

THE INFLUENCE OF BUD GRAFTING PERIODS OF QUINCE VARIETIES ON THE SURVIVAL RATE OF GRAFT COMPONENTS

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Annotation. This article examines the influence of budding periods of quince varieties Samarkandskaya krupnoplodnaya, Aromatnaya, Izobelnaya, Olmabehi, and Otlichnitsa on the survival rate of graft components on BA-29 rootstock. The research was conducted from the third ten-day period of July to the first ten-day period of September. The obtained results showed that the highest graft survival rates were observed in budding performed during August 11–20. The best results were recorded in the Samarkandskaya krupnoplodnaya variety (86.6%), Aromatnaya variety (86.0%), and Olmabehi and Otlichnitsa varieties (84.2%). The findings indicate that selecting the optimal budding period is important for producing high-quality and viable seedlings.

Keywords. Quince, BA-29 rootstock, budding, graft survival, variety, seedling, vegetative propagation, grafting period, bud.

Introduction. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4575 dated January 28, 2020, “On measures to implement the tasks defined in the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030,” identifies the prospects for developing the sector and expanding the range of new fruit plant species in our republic [1].

The results obtained by scientists indicate that, when establishing industrial orchards of the Esfahan quince variety, it is advisable to use rootstocks with different growth vigor. In particular, hawthorn is recommended as a low-vigor rootstock, QA as a medium-vigor rootstock, and BA29 as a comparatively strong-vigor rootstock [4; pp. 668–682].

Recent studies have comprehensively examined the rooting ability of quince (*Cydonia oblonga*) cuttings and the factors affecting grafting efficiency with other fruit plants. The results of experiments conducted on hardwood cuttings showed that the rooting process depends directly not only on the concentration of phytohormones, but also on the type of substrate used. In particular, a high rooting rate was recorded in the control treatment without IBA application and in cuttings planted in river sand, confirming the important role of the substrate in root formation [2; p. 11451].

During the study, the scion growth of the pear (*Pyrus communis*) cultivar ‘Doyenné du Comice’ was regularly observed, and the growth processes leading to the formation of dwarf trees were analyzed. According to the results, in dwarfing rootstocks the growth of the main scion axis stopped earlier during the vegetation period, which resulted in a smaller overall tree size. In addition, lateral branching (sylleptic branching) stimulated the formation of fruiting spurs rather than shoot elongation, while the degree of branching was lower on low-vigor rootstocks.

In grafted plants, the first flowering was observed after two years. Plants grown on low-vigor pear rootstocks and on the ‘Quince BA29’ rootstock had fewer flower clusters per tree. However, when these indicators were calculated relative to the trunk cross-sectional area, no significant difference was found [3; pp. 153–162].

Research methodology. The experiments were carried out using the methodology of Kh.Ch. Buriev et al., “Methodology for calculations and phenological observations in experiments with fruit and berry plants,” and V.F. Moiseichenko, “Methodology for accounting and observations in experiments with fruit and berry crops.” In addition to these scientists, the methods recommended by A.N. Tatarinov in “Clonal Rootstocks of Apple and Pear” were used to study the growth vigor and morpho-biological characteristics of rootstocks, budding techniques and technologies, as well as the condition of cultivar-rootstock combinations.

Research results. In this study, the influence of budding dates for grafting the quince varieties Samarkandskaya krupnoplodnaya, Aromatnaya, Izobelnaya, Olmabehi, and Otlichnitsa onto the BA-29 rootstock on the compatibility and take rate of graft components was investigated. The results showed that budding dates had a significant effect on the biological adaptation, viability, and graft-take rate of the graft components.

According to the obtained results, the highest graft-take rate in all varieties was observed when budding was carried out on August 11–20. During this period, sap movement in plants was active, and the well-developed cambium layer accelerated callus formation between the rootstock and the bud. As a result, the graft components showed a high rate of successful union.

In the Samarkandskaya krupnoplodnaya variety, the total number of successfully established buds during the August 11–20 period was 43.3, or 86.6%. In this treatment, the total number of dead buds was 6.7, which was the lowest value compared with the other dates. In the control treatment (August 1–10), the take rate was 75.8%, whereas in the optimal period this indicator was 10.8% higher. At the end of July and at the beginning of September, the take rate was 68.4% and 68.6%, respectively.

Table 1

Influence of budding dates for grafting quince varieties onto the BA-29 rootstock on the take rate of graft components (2023–2025)

Grafting date, date/month	Non-established cuttings in summer inspection, pcs	Non-established cuttings before autumn inspection, pcs	Total dead cuttings, pcs	Total established cuttings pcs	Total established cuttings %
Samarkandskaya krupnoplodnaya variety					
20–30/VII	7.5	8.3	15.8	34.2	68.4
1–10/VIII (control)	5.3	6.8	12.1	37.9	75.8
11–20/VIII	3.1	3.6	6.7	43.3	86.6
21–30/VIII	5.2	6.3	11.5	38.5	77.0
1–10/IX	7.4	8.3	15.7	34.3	68.6
Aromatnaya variety					

20-30/VII	7.6	8.1	15.7	34.3	68.6
1-10/VIII (control)	5.4	6.4	11.8	38.2	76.4
11-20/VIII	3.2	3.8	7.0	43.0	86.0
21-30/VIII	5.1	6.5	11.6	38.4	76.8
1-10/IX	7.5	8.9	16.4	33.6	67.2
Izobelnaya variety					
20-30/VII	7.5	8.8	16.3	33.7	67.4
1-10/VIII (control)	6.4	7.5	13.9	36.1	72.2
11-20/VIII	3.5	4.6	8.1	41.9	83.8
21-30/VIII	6.2	7.4	13.6	36.4	72.8
1-10/IX	8.8	9.5	18.3	31.7	63.4
Olmabehi variety					
20-30/VII	7.4	8.3	15.7	34.3	68.6
1-10/VIII (control)	6.3	7.2	13.5	36.5	73.0
11-20/VIII	3.4	4.5	7.9	42.1	84.2
21-30/VIII	6.1	7.5	13.6	36.4	72.8
1-10/IX	8.9	9.3	18.2	31.8	63.6
Otlichnitsa variety					
20-30/VII	6.9	7.8	14.7	35.3	70.6
1-10/VIII (control)	5.3	6.8	12.1	37.9	75.8
11-20/VIII	3.8	4.1	7.9	42.1	84.2
21-30/VIII	5.1	7.9	13.0	37.0	74.0
1-10/IX	7.8	8.2	16.0	34.0	68.0

The same pattern was also observed in the Aromatnaya variety. During the August 11-20 period, the take rate reached 86.0%, and the total number of dead buds was only 7.0. At the end of July, the take rate was 68.6%, while at the beginning of September it was 67.2%, which was considerably lower than in the optimal period. This indicates the importance of the most active stage of the vegetation period for budding.

High results were also recorded in the Izobelnaya variety. In particular, during the August 11-20 period, the total number of successfully established buds was 41.9, or 83.8%. In this period, the total number of dead buds was 8.1, which was lower than in the other treatments. At the beginning of September, the take rate decreased to 63.4%. This situation can be explained by the decline in cambial activity at later dates.

In the Olmabehi variety, the take rate in the optimal period was 84.2%. In this treatment, the total number of successfully established buds was 42.1, while the number of dead buds was 7.9. Compared with the control treatment, the take rate was 11.2% higher. At the end of July and at the beginning of September, the take rate was 68.6% and 63.6%, respectively.

Although the take-rate indicators of the Otlichnitsa variety were slightly lower than those of the other varieties, the best result was also observed during the August 11-20 period. In this period, the take rate was 84.2%. At the end of July and at the beginning of September, the take

rates were 70.6% and 68.0%, respectively.

During the study, the number of non-established buds was also analyzed during summer and autumn inspections. The results showed that, in all varieties, the number of buds that died before the summer and autumn inspections was minimal during the August 11–20 period. This indicates that the physiological adaptation process between the graft components proceeded actively during this specific period.

In general, the research results showed that the most suitable period for budding quince varieties onto the BA-29 rootstock is August 11–20. During this period, the take rate of the graft components was high, while the mortality rate was minimal. The results of the study have important scientific and practical significance for producing high-quality and biologically strong seedlings.

Conclusion. The budding periods of quince varieties Samarkandskaya krupnoplodnaya, Aromatnaya, Izobelnaya, Olmabehi, and Otlichnitsa on BA-29 rootstock significantly affected the survival rate of graft components. According to the research results, the highest survival rates in all varieties were observed during budding performed on August 11–20. The highest survival rates were recorded in the Samarkandskaya krupnoplodnaya variety (86.6%), Aromatnaya variety (86.0%), and Olmabehi and Otlichnitsa varieties (84.2%). Budding carried out in late July and early September resulted in lower survival rates. During the August 11–20 period, the number of dead buds observed in summer and autumn inspections was minimal, indicating good biological compatibility between graft components. For producing high-quality and viable quince seedlings, it is recommended to carry out budding on BA-29 rootstock during August 11–20.

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